

ISic1624

I.Sicily inscription 1624

Language

Punic

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Eryx

Place of origin (modern)

Erice

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Erice (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645076

Bibliography

Bisi, A.M. 1969. Frammento di stela votiva con iscrizione punica da Erice. *AION*. 19: 112-116.

Teixidor, J. 1986. Bulletin d'épigraphie sémitique. Paris. At (1972) no.130

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